

RESPONSIBILITY FOR RESEARCH DATA QUALITY IN OPEN ACCESS: A SLOVENIAN CASE

Project Open Data – action plan delivery for the open access system of research data financed from public resources in Slovenia

- ID number of project: CRP with ID V5-1018
- Budget: 60 000 EUR
- Duration: 2010-13
- Contractor: ADP

OECD declaration

Starting point

OECD principles and guidelines for access to publicly funded research data

Objective

Forming expert foundation for gradual establishment of a comprehensive system of open access to digitized data financed from public resources in Slovenia

WHOSE RESPONSIBILITY?

- researchers
- policy makers
- data creators
- data services

"This is not seen as an honorable job, it is slave labour (...)" (Miran Hladnik, Slovene literary historian).

low reputation of data related activities

monopolization of data access until exhausting its cognitive potential

LOW DATA SHARING CULTURE

ensure greater motivation credits for data producers

respect primer researchers interests

"As I see it at the institute, some of the required preservation or preparation of data for general availability would be considered as an extra obligation and additional administration unless additional funding are given.." (Sciences Institute Director's Adviser).

"Often the general thinking is that this is mine and that someone else will find something in the data that I have not seen and will publish it. It isn't necessarily the case that this is fine with everyone." (Andrej Blejec, Biologist,

MOTIVATION FOR OPEN ACCESS

DATA CREATION ISSUES

GOOD DATA

BAD DATA

researchers esteem, previous publication record, integrity

self-evident beliefs about good practices established within the scientific community

contribution of librarians as experts in general metadata

consensus within the scientific community

"Researchers who have a look at the data collection immediately see whether the data is in order or not" (Andrej Blejec, Biologist, Head of Statistical society in Slovenia).

DATA SELECTION ISSUES

insufficiently cleaned and documented data

barriers to open access

- ✗ lack of time
- ✗ little motivation

BAD DATA CAN ALSO BE INTERESTING

"Well, data are so and so, but everything is included in because bad data also say something. If data are missing you are repeatedly trying to discover and reveal why they haven't been included. Better bad data than no data." (Miran Hladnik, Slovene Literature).

"Simple, this is very simple. A good researcher has good data, a bad researcher has bad data." (Head of a research library).

"What I would like to put an emphasis on are those metadata that complement recorded materials. I think the profession has accomplished things quite well here." (Audio archive researcher).

DEMAND OF RESEARCHERS

open access requirement acceptable

under conditions: infrastructure building ESFRI financing respect for authorship